

PROCEEDINGS OF
INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON
**ADVANCED MATERIALS FOR
ENERGY AND ENVIRONMENTAL
APPLICATIONS**

(ICAMEA - 2020)

Organized by,
PG & Research Department of Physics

Thiru Kolanjiappar Govt. Arts College (Grade I)

Vriddhachalam - 606001, Tamilnadu, INDIA.

Copyright © by PHOTONICS, 2020.

This book or any part thereof may not be reproduced in any form without the written permission of the publisher.

This book cannot be sold outside the country to which it is consigned by the publisher without the prior permission of the publisher.

Information contained in this book has been published by PHOTONICS and has been obtained by its authors from sources believed to be reliable and are correct to the best of their knowledge. However, the publisher and its authors shall in no event be liable for any errors, omissions or damages arising out of use of this information and specifically disclaim any implied warranties or merchantability or fitness for any particular use.

Compiled by:

Dr. P. Anandan

Convener

ICAMEA-2020

Typesetting by:

PG and Research Department of Physics,

Thiru Kolanjiappar Government Arts College (Grade I)

Vriddhachalam – 606001

Printed by:

PG and Research Department of Physics,

Thiru Kolanjiappar Government Arts College (Grade I)

Vriddhachalam – 606001

Published by: PHOTONICS, Salem – 636 201

ISBN : 978-81-939316-1-5

Price: Rs.500/-

		Antibacterial Activity of 3-(4-(Tetrazole-1-Yl)Phenyl)-1,5-Diphenyl-1h-Pyrazole Derivatives	Pazhamalai	
225	PO164	Electrochemical properties of Zn-CdS thin films	T. Sivanesan, P. Elangovan	171
226	PO165	High performance near ultraviolet emitter based on phenanthroimidazole via substitutions at C6- and C9-positions	Jayaraman Jayabharathi, Sekar Sivaraj, Venugopal Thanikachalam, Mageswaran Vijayasri	171
227	PO166	Constructing donor-acceptor molecules using nonsymmetrical connection strategy for efficient organic emitting diodes	Jayaraman Jayabharathi, Jagathratchagan Anudeebhana, Venugopal Thanikachalam, Sekar Mathi, Shanmugam Thilagavathy	172
228	PO167	Synthesis and characterizations of zn doped SnO ₂ :TiO ₂ for gas sensor applications	P. S. Ramesh, D. Geetha, V. Vidhya	173
229	PO168	Design and analysis of an excavator bucket	K. C. Boobalan, E. Loganadhan, K. Pazhanivel	173
230	PO169	Design and analysis of car crash element	E. Arunkumar, V. Porselvan, K. Pazhanivel	174
231	PO170	CFD simulation of car HVAC pannel aiming study with different blower speed	A. Jafarullah, M. Arul, K. Pazhanivel	174
232	PO171	Characterization of wire EDM of forged components	K. Rajesh Kumar, G. Saravanan, K. Pazhanivel	175
233	PO172	Design optimization of Engine Exhaust manifold (Convergt Type)	M. Stalin, K. Pazhanivel	176
234	PO173	Design and evolution of characteristic properties of automotive wheel spoke by using aluminum alloy material	U. Arun kumar, K. Pazhanivel	176
235	PO174	Occupational heat stress assessment and defending strategies within the environment and global climate change	V. Sumathy	177
236	PO175	Synthesis and characterzation of ctab capped praseodymium oxide nanoparticles	M. Anto Milet Xavier, Dr. P. Elangovan	178
237	PO176	Synthesis and characterizaion of MnWO ₃ nanocomposites	K. Kathiresan, P. Elangovan	178
238	PO177	A study on zinc blende GaN/Al _x Ga _{1-x} N parabolic	B. Seenuvasan, P. Elangovan	179

properties of stress and displacement with Magnesium Alloy (AM 60A) and also the fillet radius is modified. The model is created using pro-e and analysis done in SOLIDWORKS software. Finally by comparison of two materials, aluminum composite material LM25 with the change in fillet radius has good fatigue life, low stress and low displacement.

PO-174

OCCUPATIONAL HEAT STRESS ASSESSMENT AND DEFENDING STRATEGIES WITHIN THE ENVIRONMENT AND GLOBAL CLIMATE CHANGE

V. Sumathy

*Department of Business Administration, Thiru Kolanjiappar Government Arts College,
Vriddhachalam, Tamilnadu, India
Email: vsumathysenthil@yahoo.co.in*

ABSTRACT

Global warming will unquestionably increase the impact of warmth on individuals who add already hot workplaces in hot climate areas. The increasing prevalence of this environmental health risk requires the development of assessment methods linked to meteorological data. Such new methods will help to reveal the dimensions of the matter and style appropriate interventions at individual, workplace and societal level. The valuation of occupational heat stress requires capacity of four thermal climate factors (air temperature, humidity, air velocity and warmth radiation); reachable atmospheric lookout data may serve this persistence. However, the utilization of meteorological data for occupational heat stress valuation is restricted because weather stations don't traditionally and directly measure some imperative climate factors, e.g. solar radiation. In addition, local workstation environmental conditions like local heat sources, metabolic heat production within the physical body, and clothing properties, all affect the exchange of temperateness between the body and the environment. A robust occupational heat stress index should properly address of these factors. This article reviews and highlights kind of selected heat stress indices, indicating their advantages and drawbacks in reference to meteorological data, local workplace environments, body heat production and thus the use of protective clothing. These heat stress and heat strain indices include Wet Bulb Globe Heat, Discomfort Index, Predicted Heat Strain index, and Worldwide Thermal Temperature Index. In some cases, individuals could also be monitored for warmth strain through physiological measurements and medical supervision before and through exposure. Relevant protective and deterrent strategies for lessening heat strain are also reviewed and projected.

Keywords: Heating, Meteorological data, Occupational and environmental health, Heat stress index, Heat strain, Protection.

PO-175